

Theory for a Single Degree of Freedom Peak Displacement Analysis of a Tunnel Liner

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28 June 2023

Report Number EBR5005

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8092085>
(Consult DOI for citation information)

Abstract

In practical design, the blast response of beams is often determined by employing simplified single degree of freedom (SDOF) models. These models use tabulated coefficients for determining equivalent SDOF mass, (nonlinear) resistance, and load. The parameters for the resistance function are also tabulated. However, existing SDOF approaches cannot be used for tunnel liners because they do not consider the soil behind the tunnel liner. This report presents a theoretical derivation extending the existing SDOF formulation to include the soil behind the liner, focusing on the peak deflection. Nonlinearity of the soil is incorporated with a secant modulus approach. The resulting equivalent SDOF soil resistance and stiffness are derived in general terms and computed numerically in the case of a simply supported beam. A description is then provided for implementing the results in a numerical time-stepping algorithm. This work is intended as a proof-of-concept study. A subsequent M.S. thesis will implement, verify, and evaluate the numerical algorithm, after which decisions can be made about subsequent research and development needs.

1. Introduction

The goal of this report is to develop a Single Degree of Freedom (SDOF) analysis approach suitable for predicting the peak deflection of tunnel liners subjected to blast loads. This goal is accomplished by extending the standard SDOF approach for blast-loaded beams to include the soil behind the liner. This is a proof-of-concept study entailing many simplifying assumptions. These assumptions are identified throughout the text **in bold** and summarized at the end of the report. The goal of the study is to determine if the concept has sufficient potential for use to merit subsequent refinements.¹

The standard SDOF model for a beam subjected to a blast load is well known. Chapter 5 of the structural dynamics textbook by Biggs (1964) is commonly referenced by the blast community. SDOF modeling is codified by the Department of Defense (2008) in Chapter 3 of manual number UFC 3-340-02, which follows Biggs's approach to a great extent. Some of the notation herein differs from Biggs's as it has been influenced by Chopra (2017, Sec 8.3.2). For instance, equivalent SDOF quantities employ a tilde (e.g., \tilde{M}) instead of a subscript "e" (e.g., M_e).

¹ Given the preliminary nature of this study, the following editorial corners have been cut. (1) Hand sketches are deemed satisfactory for now. (2) Ideally, the differential is written as "dx" with the "d" set upright and the "x" italic. However, in this manuscript it has been set at "dx" (all italic) for expediency. (3) There is a glitch in the (manual) equation numbering due to an equation added late in the editing process.

Following this introduction, the problem is defined and the governing equation of motion derived. Then, each of the individual terms is developed separately in the following order: equivalent masses, equivalent load, equivalent liner resistance, shape function, and equivalent soil resistance. Numerical values are then computed for a simply supported beam. Following this, guidelines are provided for a numerical implementation. The numerical implementation itself will be the subject of the related M.S. thesis. Lastly, the model's limitations are discussed and the report is concluded.

2. Problem Definition and Equation of Motion

The tunnel liner with soil behind it is illustrated in Fig. 1. The liner is represented as a vertical beam although this orientation can easily be changed. Fig. 1 shows **simply supported boundary conditions** for the beam, which is the assumption adopted in this report. The theory, however, applies to any combination of boundary conditions. The **soil is represented by linear distributed springs with nonlinearity accounted for by a secant modulus**. A distributed load is placed along the length of the beam. The properties of the system are as detailed in the following list. Variable dependences are given in the initial definitions but are omitted in most of the subsequent calculations.

System Properties:

- $v(x, t)$: Deformation of the beam in the y direction.
- $p(x, t)$: Applied distributed load in units of Force/Length, usually represented by separable time and space components as $p(x, t) = p_x(x) \cdot p_t(t)$.
- b : Representative width of the beam into the page (Fig. 1), for a concrete liner this can be conveniently taken as the spacing between reinforcing bars.
- L : Beam length.
- $m_L(x)$: Beam (liner) mass in units of Force/Length, typically constant and equal to the mass density multiplied by the cross-sectional area.
- $E(x)$: Beam elastic modulus, typically constant.
- $I(x)$: Beam moment of inertia, typically constant. For concrete an appropriate value should be used for the effective moment of inertia considering cracking.
- M_p : Plastic moment capacity of the beam.
- $m_s(x)$: Soil mass in units of Force/Length. Soil mass is calculated as $m_s(x) = \rho_s(x) d_e b$, where ρ_s is the soil mass density and d_e is an effective depth of soil for mass calculations. The latter is a parameter that requires calibration in the model. Although in principle d_e can be allowed to vary in x , **d_e will be taken as a constant** in subsequent calculations.
- $E_s(x)$: Young's modulus of the soil, typically constant.
- $\nu_s(x)$: Poisson's ratio of the soil, typically constant.
- $k_s(x)$: Soil elastic stiffness in units of [Force/Length]/Length (see Sec. 7).
- $f_s(x, t) = k_s(x) v(x, t)$: Soil resistance in units of Force/Length.

Fig. 1. Left: Sketch of a rectangular tunnel liner showing the segment that is represented by the SDOF model. Right: Idealized model for a wall of the liner. The beam width is b into the page.

The free body diagram for a slice of the beam of length dx is shown in Fig. 2. Dots indicate differentiation with respect to time, V represents the shear force, and M represents the moment; dV and dM are increments of shear and moment, respectively. Inertial forces are indicated by dashed arrows. **The inertial force for the soil uses one half of the soil mass** because it is assumed that one end of the soil block moves with the liner while the other end (a yet unspecified depth d_e away) does not move; the soil is assumed to move as the average of these two motions. **Damping is neglected**; this is an acceptable simplification given that we are only interested in obtaining the peak motion, which occurs in the first quarter cycle of vibration, during which any effect of damping is negligible.

Fig. 2. Free body diagram of a slice of the beam of length dx .

Equilibrium in the y -direction yields

$$p dx - dV - m_L \ddot{v} dx - m_s \frac{\ddot{v}}{2} dx - f_s dx = 0. \quad (1)$$

From beam theory $dV/dx = M''$, where the prime indicates differentiation with respect to x . Substituting this result after dividing Eq. 1 by dx and solving for p yields the following governing differential equation:

$$\left(m_L + \frac{m_s}{2}\right) \ddot{v} + M'' + f_s = p. \quad (2)$$

To solve this equation with an approximate SDOF approach, the method of separation of variables is

used, whereby the transverse deflection of the liner is represented by separate time and space components as

$$v(x, t) = \phi(x)z(t), \quad (3)$$

or simply

$$v = \phi z, \quad (4)$$

where ϕ is the shape function and is normalized to a maximum value of unity and z is the deflection of the liner at the location where the shape function takes on the value of unity. For example, for a simply supported beam acted upon by a uniform load, z is measured at $x = L/2$, i.e., mid-span or mid-height. Other requirements for the shape function are provided in Sec. 6. Substituting Eq. 4 in Eq. 2 yields the following expression:

$$\left(m_L + \frac{m_s}{2}\right) \phi \ddot{z} + M'' + f_s = p. \quad (5)$$

Subsequently satisfying this equation in weak form (principle of virtual displacements) with a variation of displacement $\delta v = \phi \delta z$ yields the following expression:

$$\left\{ \int_L \left[\left(\left(m_L + \frac{m_s}{2}\right) \phi \ddot{z} + M'' + f_s - p \right) \phi dx \right] \delta z = 0. \quad (6)$$

Because the variation δz is arbitrary, the quantity inside the curly brackets must be zero. Taking this into account then rearranging terms yields the following equivalent SDOF equation of motion:

$$\left[\underbrace{\int_L m_L \phi^2 dx}_{\tilde{M}_L} + \underbrace{\int_L \frac{m_s}{2} \phi^2 dx}_{\tilde{M}_s} \right] \ddot{z} + \underbrace{\int_L M'' \phi dx}_{\tilde{R}_L} + \underbrace{\int_L f_s \phi dx}_{\tilde{R}_s} = \underbrace{\int_L p \phi dx}_{\tilde{P}}, \quad (7)$$

or

$$\underbrace{(\tilde{M}_L + \tilde{M}_s)}_{\tilde{M}} \ddot{z} + \tilde{R}_L + \tilde{R}_s = \tilde{P}, \quad (8)$$

where the tilde indicates an equivalent SDOF quantity. Thus, \tilde{M} is the equivalent mass, equal to the sum of the equivalent liner mass \tilde{M}_L and the equivalent soil mass \tilde{M}_s , \tilde{R}_L is the equivalent liner resistance, \tilde{R}_s is the equivalent soil resistance, and \tilde{P} is the equivalent load. Although it is not shown explicitly, both the liner and soil resistance depend on deflection z . In the following sections, each of the terms in Eq. 8 will be discussed in detail (making additional assumptions) in the following order: equivalent masses, equivalent liner resistance, selection of shape function (which changes depending on the nonlinear behavior of the liner resistance), and soil resistance.

3. Equivalent Masses

In the case of **uniform mass**, the equivalent masses identified in Eq. 7 simplify as follows:

$$\tilde{M}_L = m_L \int_L \phi^2 dx \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{M}_S = \frac{m_S}{2} \int_L \phi^2 dx. \quad (10)$$

Biggs writes the equivalent liner mass in terms of a tabulated mass constant (K_M) such that

$$\tilde{M}_L = K_M M_L, \quad (11)$$

where M_L is the total mass of the liner. Using a similar approach, we can say for the soil that

$$\tilde{M}_S = K_M \frac{M_S}{2}, \quad (12)$$

where M_S is total mass of the soil. Equating Eqs. 9 and 11, and recalling that the total mass is $m_L L$, we obtain

$$m_L \int_L \phi^2 dx = K_M m_L L, \quad (13)$$

which can be solved for K_M to obtain

$$K_M = \frac{1}{L} \int_L \phi^2 dx. \quad (14)$$

A similar procedure with Eqs. 10 and 12 yields the same result for the equivalent soil mass. K_M is tabulated for common shape functions (e.g., Biggs's Table 1.5). These tabulated values can be used for both the liner and soil masses.

4. Equivalent Load

The equivalent load simplifies as follows in the case of **uniform loading**:

$$\tilde{P} = p \int_L \phi dx. \quad (15)$$

Biggs writes this quantity in terms of a tabulated load constant (K_L) and the total load $P = pL$ such that

$$\tilde{P} = K_L P = K_L p L. \quad (16)$$

Equating the two previous equations yields the following expression

$$p \int_L \phi dx = K_L p L, \quad (17)$$

which can be solved for K_L to obtain

$$K_L = \frac{1}{L} \int_L \phi \, dx. \quad (18)$$

K_L is tabulated for common shape functions (E.g., Biggs's Table 1.5).

5. Equivalent Liner Resistance

The liner resistance can be formulated in two ways. The first uses the expression for equivalent liner resistance from Eq. 7 and is consistent with Biggs's formulation, including readily available tabulated values for equivalent SDOF constants for a wide variety of boundary conditions. This formulation depends on knowing the load-deflection curve (resistance function) of the beam. The second formulation relates to the flexural stiffness EI and the moment-curvature relation of the cross section.

First formulation (Resistance Function)

As stated in Eq. 7 the expression for the equivalent liner resistance is

$$\tilde{R}_L = \int_L M'' \phi \, dx. \quad (19)$$

Recall from beam theory for a statically loaded beam without soil that the distributed load applied to the beam is equal to the second derivative of its bending moment M'' . If the load causing internal moments is subsequently assumed to be equal to p , then $M'' = p$ (this result is evident from Eq. 2 if the dynamic term is neglected and the soil term removed). In SDOF methods without soil, this approximation is known to result in little error. However, for a statically loaded beam on an elastic foundation, the same approximation is not guaranteed to be adequate. This difficulty can be seen from Eq. 2, which after neglecting dynamic terms but maintaining the soil resistance, implies that $M'' = p - f_s$. Because f_s is expected to have a significant influence on the response, it is clear that $M'' \neq p$. Despite this fact, to maintain consistency with previous results, it will be assumed that **the second derivative of the bending moment in the soil-supported beam is proportional to the applied load**. This is equivalent to stating that $M'' = p - f_s \approx a p$, where a is a proportionality constant that will cancel out from subsequent calculations. It remains to be seen whether this assumption is adequate in the case of a soil-supported beam.

After employing the assumption just stated, Eq. 19 becomes

$$\tilde{R}_L = \int_L a p \phi \, dx. \quad (20)$$

Following Biggs's approach, the equivalent resistance can be written in terms of a tabulated resistance constant (K_R) as follows:

$$\tilde{R}_L = K_R R_L, \quad (21)$$

where R_L represents the total resistance of the liner. From the previous explanation it follows that $R_L =$

$\int_L M'' dx = \int_L a p dx$. Substituting this result into Eq. 21, equating the result to Eq. 20, and cancelling the constant a yields

$$\int_L p \phi dx = K_R \int_L p dx. \quad (22)$$

Assuming the load to be uniform and solving for K_R yields

$$K_R = \frac{1}{L} \int_L \phi dx. \quad (23)$$

Comparing Eqs. 18 and 23 it is clear that $K_L = K_R$. This result is stated by Biggs (p. 204) but never proven.

The resistance R_L is computed directly as a load-deflection curve, commonly called a “resistance function”, computed by an analysis of an elastic beam with plastic hinges. A typical bilinear resistance function is shown in Fig. 3. The ultimate load R_u and the liner stiffness k_L are tabulated by Biggs for a variety of boundary conditions (e.g., Table 5.1). Bear in mind that the liner stiffness (k_L), which is lower case, should not be confused with the load factor (K_L), which is upper case. Some combinations of boundary conditions, e.g., fixed ends, will yield a resistance function with three linear segments. These are sometimes approximated by bilinear resistance functions.

Fig. 3. Typical bi-linear resistance function.

Second Formulation (Moment-Curvature)

To obtain the second formulation, Eq. 19 can be rewritten by using integration by parts² twice to yield

$$\tilde{R}_L = \int_L M \phi'' dx. \quad (24)$$

Recall that from beam theory $M = EI \phi$, where ϕ is the curvature, and that for small deflections $\phi = v''$. Substituting these results into Eq. 24 and recalling that $v = \phi z$ (Eq. 4),

² Integration by parts states that $\int u dv = uv - \int v du$. The term uv is evaluated at the boundary and for all common structural supports (e.g., pinned and fixed ends) this term vanishes. See Rodriguez-Nikl (2006, 26) for details.

$$\tilde{R}_L = \underbrace{\int_L EI (\phi'')^2 dx}_z. \quad (25)$$

where the quantity \tilde{k}_L is the equivalent liner stiffness. The same expression can be obtained directly from virtual displacements, recognizing that the virtual internal strain energy in bending is $\int_L M \delta\phi dx$ and making the same substitutions that were made into Eq. 25 (see Chopra 2017, Sec. 8.3.2). Having defined the liner stiffness as

$$\tilde{k}_L = \int_L EI (\phi'')^2 dx, \quad (26)$$

the liner resistance can be written as follows:

$$\tilde{R}_L = \tilde{k}_L z. \quad (27)$$

In the same way that the resistance function can be nonlinear, EI , and thus the equivalent stiffness, can vary with deflection. However, accommodating nonlinearity is more difficult in this formulation.

6. Shape Function as a Function of Resistance

Any shape function ϕ can be chosen as long as it satisfies the displacement boundary conditions, e.g., zero displacement and unrestrained rotation at simply supported ends. The approximation is best if the shape function also satisfies the force boundary conditions, e.g., zero moment at simply supported ends (Chopra 2017, Sec. 8.6). To accomplish both conditions in a straightforward manner, it is common for beams that are not resting on an elastic foundation to adopt a shape function proportional to the deflected shape of the beam subjected to the load p applied statically. This assumption is consistent with the assumed relation between M'' and p that was described in the previous section. As was previously stated (Sec. 2), the shape function should be normalized to a maximum value of unity. Once this is done, z becomes the reference deflection at the location of maximum deflection.

In this report, **the shape function computed without an elastic foundation will be used for the beam that is supported by an elastic foundation.** This approach is consistent with the previous assumption that $M'' = a p$. For the beam resting on an elastic foundation, the discrepancy between the exact and assumed shape function will be greater than for the beam alone. However, the assumed shape function will satisfy both displacement and force boundary conditions and thus can be expected to provide a good estimate of period (Chopra 2017, Sec. 8.6) and subsequently displacements.

Recall from Fig. 3, that the resistance function is comprised of piecewise linear segments. It is standard practice to use a different shape function for each segment of the resistance function, corresponding to the formation of a plastic mechanism. The evolution of the shape function is described here for a simply supported beam. The same principles apply to other boundary conditions. In the initial elastic region, the elastic shape function (ϕ_e) is given by the deflected shape of the simply supported beam (normalized to a maximum value of unity at midspan):

$$\phi_e = \frac{16x}{5L^4} (L^3 - 2Lx^2 + x^3). \quad (28)$$

When the moment at midspan reaches the yield moment, a plastic hinge will form at that location. The resulting beam forms a mechanism and subsequently deforms as a rigid body. In this region, the plastic shape function (ϕ_p) is:

$$\phi_p = \begin{cases} 2\frac{x}{L}, & x < \frac{L}{2} \\ 2\left(1 - \frac{x}{L}\right), & x \geq \frac{L}{2} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

This shape function also attains a maximum value of unity (at midspan). The two shape functions are illustrated in Fig. 4. Following from these shape functions and Eq. 4 the deflection (Fig. 5) is given by

$$v = \begin{cases} \phi_e z, & z < z_y \\ \phi_e z_y + \phi_p (z - z_y), & z \geq z_y, \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

where the yield deflection is

$$v_y = \phi_e z_y. \quad (31)$$

The change in shape function must be accounted for in all expressions. Anywhere that ϕ appears in an expression, either ϕ_e or ϕ_p should be substituted as appropriate. This substitution will be illustrated shortly for the simply supported beam. As Biggs acknowledges, the change of shape function “implies a sudden change in the characteristics of the dynamic system. Although clearly, this is not correct, the error resulting from this approximation is tolerable, and is in fact necessary if we are to obtain a practical solution” (207).

Fig. 4. Pre- and post-yield shape functions

Fig. 5. Liner displacement (a) before, (b) at, and (c) after yield

7. Equivalent Soil Resistance

Introduction

The equivalent soil resistance is given in Eq. 7 by

$$\tilde{R}_s = \int_L f_s \phi dx. \quad (32)$$

For a distributed elastic foundation, the resistance is written in terms of the soil stiffness and the liner deflection as follows

$$f_s = k_s v. \quad (33)$$

The stiffness will be computed from the following expression proposed by Vesić (1963, eq 24) for a beam resting on a semi-infinite elastic foundation:

$$k_s = 0.65 \sqrt[12]{\frac{\alpha E_s B^4}{EI}} \left(\frac{\alpha E_s}{1 - \nu_s^2} \right). \quad (34)$$

This **stiffness is assumed to be constant over the length of the beam**. Some of the notation in Eq. 34 has been modified slightly from the original to agree with the notation in this report. The term B is defined as the width of the beam. Because in this problem we have a continuous liner with no discrete endpoint it is not clear what value should be used for B . Thus, B will be considered as a fitting parameter in our model. A reduction factor α has been added to the soil modulus to account for soil nonlinearity. Nonlinearity arises from two sources: nonlinearity of the soil itself and non-uniform compression of the soil. To visualize the latter effect, note that in Fig 5 the soil near midspan will compress considerably more than the soil near the supports. **Lumping both sources of nonlinearity together with a secant modulus** approach is clearly an oversimplification. Due to this, the research question at this stage is whether the model will work well with a reasonable value of α and if so, whether it can be calibrated to produce acceptable predictions.

Strictly speaking, Eq. 34 is for an infinite beam on a semi-infinite foundation. However, according to Vesić Eq. 34 equation can be employed with acceptable accuracy as long as $\lambda L_f > 2.25$, where

$$\lambda = \sqrt[4]{\frac{k_s}{4EI}}, \quad (34b)$$

and L_f is the free length from the end of the beam to the nearest point force. This assumption would be met for an infinite beam with a single point load applied at midspan (as would be the case for smaller surface charges). However, both the distributed load and the point loads at the simple supports result in $L_e = 0$. Vesić suggests an approach for approximating internal bending moments even in the case of point loads at the ends, but there is no such guidance for distributed loads. Nonetheless, because SDOF methods do not depend on the exact knowledge of internal forces, perhaps the use of Eq. 34 is still acceptable for the estimation of peak deflection within the context of a SDOF method. **The appropriateness of Eq. 34 for this application remains to be assessed in proper detail.**

Next, the equivalent soil resistance will be developed according to the two formulations of the liner resistance, beginning with the second formulation because it follows directly from the equations just presented. The second formulation will be used in subsequent calculations.

Equivalent Soil Spring Stiffness, Second Formulation

To begin the derivation, Eqs. 32 and 33 are combined. Subsequently recognizing that k_s is constant results in the following expression:

$$\tilde{R}_s = k_s \int_L v \phi dx. \quad (35)$$

This equation applies for both the pre- and post-yield stages.

Prior to Yield

To determine the equivalent soil resistance before the liner yields, the first part of Eq. 30 is incorporated into Eq. 35 (using the shape function ϕ_e) to obtain

$$\tilde{R}_s = \underbrace{k_s \int_L \phi_e^2 dx}_{\tilde{k}_{se}} z, \quad (36)$$

where the equivalent soil stiffness during elastic liner behavior has been defined as

$$\tilde{k}_{se} = k_s \int_L \phi_e^2 dx. \quad (37)$$

Post-Yield

To determine the equivalent soil resistance after the liner yields, the second part of Eq. 30 is incorporated into Eq. 35 (using shape function ϕ_p anywhere ϕ appears) to obtain

$$\tilde{R}_s = k_s \int_L [\phi_e z_y + \phi_p (z - z_y)] \phi_p dx, \quad (38)$$

which simplifies to

$$\tilde{R}_s = \underbrace{k_s \int_L \phi_e \phi_p dx}_{\tilde{R}_{s py}} z_y + \underbrace{k_s \int_L \phi_p^2 dx}_{\tilde{k}_{sp}} (z - z_y), \quad (39)$$

where the soil resistance immediately after the liner yields has been defined as

$$\tilde{R}_{s py} = k_s \int_L \phi_e \phi_p dx z_y, \quad (40)$$

and the equivalent soil stiffness during plastic liner behavior has been defined as

$$\tilde{k}_{sp} = k_s \int_L \phi_p^2 dx. \quad (41)$$

Since Eqs. 37 and 41 are similar, the following single equation can be written for the equivalent soil stiffness with the understanding that the appropriate shape function should be used:

$$\tilde{k}_s = k_s \int_L \phi^2 dx. \quad (42)$$

Note that the integral in Eqs. 37, 41, and 42 is the same as the mass factor given by Eq. 14. This is purely a coincidence.

The equivalent soil resistance is illustrated in Fig 6. It is important to reiterate that the soil is assumed to be elastic with a reduced secant modulus to accommodate for soil nonlinearity and a variation of soil compression along the length of the beam. The drop in value and the change in slope illustrated in Fig. 6 arise solely from the change in shape function due to liner yielding. The sudden drop in soil resistance at z_y is odd but it is consistent with the SDOF approach as was acknowledged at the end of Sec. 6.

Fig. 6. Equivalent soil resistance

Equivalent Soil Spring Stiffness, First Formulation

In the interest of using the same notation as Biggs, the previous calculations can be reinterpreted according to his formulation. This formulation is an impractical technicality because there is no independent way of obtaining a resistance function for the soil analogous to Fig. 3. To begin the derivation, note that the total soil resistance is given by

$$R_s = \int_L f_s dx. \quad (43)$$

Pre-Yield

Prior to yielding of the liner, obtaining the first formulation requires writing the equivalent soil resistance as the product of a factor K_s and the total soil resistance R_s as follows:

$$\tilde{R}_s = K_s R_s \quad (44)$$

where the factor K_s will need to be determined. Substituting Eq. 33 and then Eq. 30 (for $z \leq z_y$) into Eq. 43 results in

$$R_s = \int_L f_s dx = k_s \int_L v dx = k_s \int_L \phi_e dx z. \quad (45)$$

Substituting Eqs. 36 and 45 into Eq. 44 yields the following

$$k_s \int_L \phi_e^2 dx z = K_s \left[k_s \int_L \phi_e dx z \right]. \quad (46)$$

Solving for K_s results in the following expression:

$$K_s = \frac{\int_L \phi_e^2 dx}{\int_L \phi_e dx}. \quad (47)$$

Post-Yield

After the liner yields the post-yield increments in soil resistance and equivalent soil resistance are compared as follows:

$$\tilde{R}_s - \tilde{R}_{syp} = K_s [R_s - R_{sy}]. \quad (48)$$

Substituting z_y into Eq. 45 yields the following expression for the value of the soil resistance when the liner yields:

$$R_{sy} = k_s \int_L \phi_e dx z_y. \quad (49)$$

Eq. 48, solved for K_s is

$$K_s = \frac{\tilde{R}_s - \tilde{R}_{syp}}{R_s - R_{sy}}. \quad (50)$$

Substituting Eqs. 33 and then 30 (for $z > z_y$) into Eq. 43 yields

$$R_s = \int_L f_s dx = k_s \int_L v dx = k_s \int_L \phi_e z_y + \phi_p (z - z_y) dx \quad (51)$$

Using Eq. 49 and 51 for the denominator of Eq. 50 and Eq. 39 for the numerator, results in the following expression:

$$K_s = \frac{k_s \int_L \phi_p^2 dx (z - z_y)}{k_s \int_L \phi_p dx (z - z_y)}. \quad (52)$$

Cancelling terms yields the following result:

$$K_s = \frac{\int_L \phi_p^2 dx}{\int_L \phi_p dx}. \quad (53)$$

Since Eqs. 47 and 53 are similar, a general equation can be written for the equivalent soil stiffness with the understanding that the appropriate shape function should be used:

$$K_s = \frac{\int_L \phi^2 dx}{\int_L \phi dx}. \quad (54)$$

Note that, purely by coincidence

$$K_s = \frac{K_M}{K_L}. \quad (55)$$

Once again, this result is of no practical value since the liner resistance R_s cannot be obtained independently in the same way as the resistance function. Perhaps subsequent developments can render this approach more useful.

8. Computed Results for the Simply Supported Beam

Prior to Yield

Values are computed for various equivalent SDOF parameters for the pre- and post-yield conditions for a simply supported beam. Before yield, the shape function is given by Eq. 28. Substituting this shape function in Eq. 14 yields the following value for the mass factor:

$$K_M = \frac{3968}{7875} = 0.504. \quad (56)$$

Substituting the shape function into Eq. 18 yields the following value for the load and resistance factor:

$$K_L = \frac{16}{25} = 0.64. \quad (57)$$

These two factors are consistent with the values provided by Biggs (Table 5.1).

The resistance function values in the first formulation, for constant EI are found from fundamental beam theory. Recall that in a simply supported beam subjected to a uniform load w , the maximum moment is $wL^2/8$ and the maximum resistance is reached when the moment reaches the plastic moment capacity of the cross section M_p (assuming there is **no shear failure**). Solving for the maximum load wL yields the following value for the ultimate resistance:

$$R_u = \frac{8M_p}{L}. \quad (58)$$

The stiffness is found from the maximum deflection of a simply supported beam: $5wL^4/384EI$. The stiffness is the load wL divided by the deflection, yielding the following value:

$$k_L = \frac{384 EI}{5L^3}. \quad (59)$$

Once again, these values are consistent with those provided by Biggs (Table 5.1). The deflection at yield is $z_y = R_u/k_L$ as illustrated in Fig. 3.

For the second formulation, the value of the equivalent liner stiffness for constant EI is found by evaluating Eq. 26 to obtain

$$\tilde{k}_L = \frac{6144 EI}{125 L^3} = 49.152 \frac{EI}{L^3}. \quad (60)$$

Note that the equivalent stiffness (Eq. 60) divided by the real stiffness (Eq. 59) is equal to K_L (Eq. 57), which is expected given that the two formulations are consistent.

For the soil, from Eq. 55 for the first formulation,

$$K_s = \frac{248}{315} = 0.787, \quad (61)$$

and from Eq. 37 from the second formulation,

$$\tilde{k}_{se} = \frac{3968 k_s L}{7875} = 0.504 k_s L. \quad (62)$$

Post-Yield

To find the post-yield values, the same procedure is followed but substituting now the shape function given by Eq. 29. Substituting this shape function in Eq. 14 yields the following value for the mass factor:

$$K_M = \frac{1}{3} = 0.333. \quad (63)$$

Substituting the shape function in Eq. 18 yields the following value for the load and resistance factor:

$$K_L = \frac{1}{2} = 0.50. \quad (64)$$

For the second formulation, the value of the equivalent stiffness is found by evaluating Eq. 26 to obtain

$$\tilde{k}_L = 0. \quad (65)$$

This result is consistent with Fig. 3 and the knowledge that the beam forms a mechanism with zero stiffness after yield.

For the soil, from Eq. 55 for the first formulation,

$$K_s = \frac{2}{3} = 0.667. \quad (66)$$

For the second formulation, from Eq. 41,

$$\tilde{k}_{sp} = \frac{k_s L}{3} = 0.333 k_s L, \quad (67)$$

And from Eq. 40,

$$\tilde{R}_{spp} = \frac{61 k_s L z_y}{150} = 0.407 k_s L z_y. \quad (68)$$

The values computed in this section will be used in the numerical implementation that is detailed next.

9. Numerical Implementation

The previous formulation needs to be implemented in an explicit numerical time-stepping algorithm that uses the acceleration at the beginning of a time step to compute the resulting deflection at the end of the time step. In what follows, the start of the current timestep will be denoted with a subscript i and the end of the current timestep will be denoted with a subscript $i + 1$. The beginning of the previous time step is denoted with a subscript $i - 1$. The acceleration at the beginning of a given time step is computed by solving Eq. 8 for \ddot{z} as follows,

$$\ddot{z}_i = \frac{\tilde{P}(t_i) - \tilde{R}_L(z_i) - \tilde{R}_s(z_i)}{\tilde{M}_L + \tilde{M}_s}, \quad (69)$$

and then substituting Eqs. 11, 12, and 16 into Eq. 69, to obtain

$$\ddot{z}_i = \frac{K_L p(t_i) L - \tilde{R}_L(z_i) - \tilde{R}_s(z_i)}{K_M [M_L + 0.5 M_S]}, \quad (70)$$

where from Eq. 21 and Fig. 3

$$\tilde{R}_L(z_i) = \begin{cases} K_L k_L z_i, & z \leq z_y \\ K_L R_w, & z > z_y \end{cases} \quad (71)$$

and from Eqs. 36 and 39

$$\tilde{R}_s(z_i) = \begin{cases} \tilde{k}_{se} z_i, & z \leq z_y \\ (\tilde{R}_{spp} + \tilde{k}_{sp}(z_i - z_y)), & z > z_y \end{cases}. \quad (72)$$

The resulting algorithm is structured as follows:

1. Define all physical parameters for the load, liner, and soil (see Sec. 2).
2. Define the three fitting parameters: d_e (see the definition of m_s in Sec. 2), B (see Eq. 34), and α (see Eq. 34).
3. Assume that the system starts at rest, i.e., $z(0) = \dot{z}(0) = 0$.
4. Start with the pre-yield equivalent SDOF values as computed in Sec. 8.
5. Select an appropriate time-stepping method and time step Δt (the subsequent M.S. thesis uses the method defined by Biggs in Sec. 1.2, which is briefly described below).
6. Implement the time-stepping algorithm:

- a. The acceleration at the start of each time step (i) is obtained from Eqs. 70 to 72.
- b. Use \ddot{z}_i to compute z_{i+1} as dictated by the chosen time-stepping method (the method described by Biggs uses time steps i and $i - 1$ to compute time step $i + 1$ as given in Eq. 73).
- c. Once z_{i+1} exceeds the yield deflection z_y (alternatively if the resistance exceeds the ultimate resistance R_u) switch to the post-yield equivalent SDOF values as computed in Sec. 8.
- d. Repeat the process until the maximum deflection has been reached ($z_{i+1} - z_i < 0$). Once this occurs, terminate the analysis. Since **unloading is not defined** in this approach, any subsequent values are meaningless.

The updating equation provided by Biggs (Eq. 1.5) is as follows:

$$z_{i+1} = 2z_i - z_{i-1} + \ddot{z}_i \Delta t. \quad (73)$$

Note that this method uses the two previous time steps in the updating equation, requiring a special equation for the first time step. For additional details, including special equations for the first time step, the reader is referred to Biggs's Sec. 1.2.

10. Assumptions and Limitations

Many assumptions and limitations have been identified in **bold** previously in the text; other limitations that did not emerge naturally from the derivation can also be identified. These limitations are now summarized and expanded upon. The limitations are organized by topic and within each topic by importance in descending order.

General Limitations

- The SDOF approach cannot handle localized failure modes such as breach and spall. This is a major limitation as it is fundamental to the chosen method. Localized failure modes cannot be studied with SDOF methods.
- The shape function is proportional to the static displaced shape of the beam without soil. This is a major assumption that was made to maintain consistency with existing approaches. However, it is not clear that this choice is correct. Further investigation on this matter is necessary.
- Simply supported boundary conditions have been employed. This assumption is not strictly correct since the liner elements adjoining the segment being analyzed provide significant resistance to rotation. Different boundary conditions can be tested through different shape functions and resistance functions.
- Neither reactions nor internal forces have been addressed. There are existing approaches that can be employed to find internal forces in the absence of soil (e.g., equivalent static force). However, as is described below in the section on soil, the calculation of internal forces with an elastic foundation is complicated due to the presence of forces near the end of the beam. Thus it is not yet clear how to compute internal forces or reactions in the soil-supported beam.
- The unloading behavior has not been defined. Once again, this omission is acceptable given the goal of estimating the peak deflection. Including unloading, which would be necessary to estimate the residual displacement, would require enhancements to the soil force (f_s) and the

resistance function (Fig. 3). Enhancements to the resistance function would imply the addition of an appropriate hysteretic law. Enhancements to the soil force would require original research and development. The possibility of a gap opening between the liner and the soil should be considered in this case.

- Damping has been neglected. Damping has been neglected because the main objective is estimation of the peak deflection, which occurs during the first quarter cycle of the response, during which time the effect of damping is negligible. Including damping would require modifications to Fig. 1 and Eq. 2.

Liner

- It has been assumed that the internal forces (M'') are proportional to the applied load. This assumption is typically made when there is no soil behind the beam. The same assumption was used for convenience in this derivation, but it is not clear whether the assumption is sufficiently accurate. Subsequent developments should consider other alternatives.
- The liner has been assumed to be a one-way element. This assumption appears to be justified because the element of the liner being analyzed, e.g., the vertical wall, is supported along two edges by the other elements of the liner, e.g., the roof and floor, while the other edges are not supported. However, a two-way assumption is also reasonable given that deflection will be maximum near the charge and will taper to zero in all directions. A two-way assumption should be considered in subsequent developments. These two cases are illustrated in Fig. 7.
- The behavior has been assumed to be governed by flexure. Should it be necessary, other global failure modes such as direct or diagonal shear can be incorporated with a modified resistance function. This is consistent with standard practice.
- A uniform mass has been assumed for the liner. This is a reasonable assumption that covers most practical cases. Should one wish to do so, this limitation can be relaxed by rewriting and reevaluating Eq. 9 with the mass inside the integral.

Fig 7. View from inside the tunnel towards the liner segment being analyzed. Should it be a one-way element of width b or a two-way element of width closer to B ?

Load

- The load has been assumed to be uniform. This is a reasonable assumption for a far-field, large charge. It may be necessary to relax this limitation inside a tunnel. It may also be necessary to relax this assumption to be able to consider smaller charges detonated closer to the liner, such as personnel borne improvised explosive devices (PBIEDs). A PBIED may be represented by a point charge (which could be handled easily with a Dirac delta function in the integral) or some other shape such as a triangular load. In any case, with PBIEDs the possibility of breach and spall are higher. Breach and spall cannot be handled by SDOF methods.

Soil

- Several limitations of Eq. 34 have been identified in Sec. 7 related to the small (or zero) distance from the edge of the beam to the first load. The use of this equation requires further thought and consideration.
- The effective depth (d_e) has been assumed to be constant. It is not clear that this should be the case since the depths of soil that is engaged dynamically probably depends on the deflection of the liner. Other assumptions can certainly be tested, e.g., d_e being proportional to the shape function, although a balance should be sought between accuracy and simplicity.
- The soil has been treated as linear with a secant modulus to account for both material nonlinearity and unequal compression of soil behind the liner. The use of improved soil models could be explored at the expense of model simplicity.
- The stiffness of the soil is assumed to be constant over the length of the liner. This assumption is reasonable but can be relaxed relatively by evaluating Eq. 35 with k_s inside the integral.
- Uniform mass has been assumed for the soil. This is a reasonable assumption that covers most practical cases. Should one wish to do so, this limitation can be relaxed by rewriting and reevaluating Eq. 10 with the mass inside the integral.
- The inertial force of the soil uses half of the soil mass. Changing this assumption is trivial.

11. Summary and Conclusion

The overarching motivation behind this study is to explore whether SDOF approaches can be used to analyze the blast loading response of tunnel liners. The goal of this report has been to expand the existing approach for SDOF analysis of beams to include the soil behind the liner. The main contribution has been the addition of the soil as an elastic foundation and the subsequent derivation of the equivalent SDOF terms, focusing on the deflection response. The report has been divided into the following main sections:

- Sec.1: Introduction.
- Sec. 2: Problem definition and governing differential equation.
- Sec. 3-7: Additional details for each of the terms of the differential equation (equivalent masses, equivalent load, equivalent liner resistance, shape function, and equivalent soil resistance).
- Sec. 8: Numerical values for simply supported boundary conditions.
- Sec. 9: Guidelines for a numerical implementation.
- Sec. 10: Assumptions and limitations.

A subsequent M.S. thesis will employ the numerical model to verify and characterize its behavior.

12. References

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13. Acknowledgement

This work was carried out with support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI). The contents of this report reflect the views of the authors, who are responsible for the facts and the accuracy of the information presented herein. This document is disseminated in the interest of information exchange. The report is funded, partially or entirely, by a grant from the U.S. Department of Transportation’s University Transportation Centers Program. However, the U.S. Government assumes no liability for the contents or use thereof.